

STATE CADASTRE REGISTRATION OF ENERGY FACILITIES

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State cadastral registration of land plots occupied by energy facilities is one of the necessary conditions for ensuring the effective functioning of the energy sector of the economy of Uzbekistan.

According to the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, energy lands include lands that are used or intended to ensure the activities of organizations and (or) the operation of energy facilities. For these purposes, land plots can be provided, firstly, for the placement of hydroelectric power plants, nuclear power plants, nuclear installations, storage facilities for nuclear materials and radioactive substances, radioactive waste storage facilities, thermal stations and other power plants, facilities and facilities serving them. Moreover, secondly, for the placement of electric grid facilities and other electric power facilities defined by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the electric power industry.

State cadastre of energy objects procedure:

- Maintaining the state cadastre of energy objects, taking into account the list of all types of energy objects, their quantity and quality descriptions, environmental and economic evaluation of objects, as well as collecting, analyzing, processing, systematizing, storing, updating the cadastral information and providing it to interested users in the manner prescribed by law includes.
- The list of energy objects is the basis for taking into account their quantity and quality descriptions and their ecological and economic evaluation.
- All types of energy facilities are included in the initial list. In this, the main indicators are recorded; the composition of these indicators is determined by the relevant normative documents approved by the state-joint-stock company "Uzbekenergo" in agreement with the state committee "Ergeodezkadastr". According to the results of inclusion in the list, a passport will be drawn up for each object.
- The basic accounting of the quantity and quality descriptions is carried out for each energy facility commissioned and operating at the time of accounting.
- Further changes in the description of energy objects are recorded in the current accounting.

- Taking into account the quantitative and qualitative descriptions of energy objects includes their classification according to economic, technological and ecological characteristics, their composition is determined in the normative documents on maintaining the state cadastre of energy objects.
- In order to take into account the quantitative and qualitative descriptions of energy objects, technical parameters and formats of providing cadastral information will be developed by the state-joint-stock company "Uzbekenergo" in agreement with the state committee "Ergeodezkadastr".
- Accounting information written in the cadastral book of the enterprise and entered into AIS (automated information system) of the state cadaster of energy objects.
- Economic evaluation of energy objects is carried out to assess the value of each object for taxation, privatization and other purposes.
- Economic evaluation of energy objects is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by law, taking into account their characteristics.
- The heads of the structural divisions of the state-joint-stock company "Uzbekenergo" that maintain the state cadaster of energy objects are responsible for the reliability of cadastral information of energy objects.

As rightly noted in the scientific literature in relation to the lands of the electric power industry, the data of the State (national) report cannot give an unambiguous idea of the total area of land located exactly under the objects of the electric power industry, since, for example, linear electric grid facilities can be located on lands of various categories, as well as in state, municipal and private ownership. This remark applies to the energy lands in general.

When conducting state cadastral registration of land plots occupied by energy facilities, the most problematic are land plots occupied by power lines that are part of the power grid, as well as other linear energy facilities. This is due to the length of such facilities and their location on a significant number of land plots, the rights to which belong to other persons both on the right of ownership and on other rights (lease right, right of permanent (perpetual) use).

Specialists single out, in particular, problems in carrying out cadastral registration and registration of land plots under power transmission towers. In these cases, it is necessary to carry out cadastral work in relation to land plots, the total length of which, as a rule, is more than several thousand kilometers. At the same time, power lines can pass through several settlements, in different districts, which means a different process for registering land plots. Since each district has its own system for receiving boundary plans, in addition, the linear

facility passes through different quarters, which means the preparation of boundary plans on each of them, which meets the requirements for the preparation of boundary plans. In the quarter, the poles are located on land that is in state or municipal ownership, or the poles fall on land plots that owned by someone or are already on the cadastral register. Thus, the process of drawing up boundary plans and putting land plots on cadastral registration becomes much more complicated, given the total length of the lines.

The cadastral registration of land plots occupied by linear objects remains unregulated, that the specifics of the implementation of cadastral registration of certain types of structures (linear, etc.) and land plots on which such structures are located, accounting of parts of these land plots can be established by the regulatory authority legal regulation in the field of cadastral relations. Nevertheless, today there is still no regulatory legal act establishing the features of cadastral registration of land plots on which linear objects are located.

Currently, the Ministry of Economic Development of Uzbekistan is developing a departmental regulatory legal act that establishes the specifics of the implementation of cadastral registration of certain types of structures (linear and the like) and land plots on which such structures are located, as well as accounting for parts of these land plots and restrictions resulting from the location such facilities on these land plots for the implementation of the action plan ("road map") "Improving the quality of public services in the field of state cadastral registration of real estate and state registration of rights to real estate and transactions with it", approved by the order of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

References:

1. <https://lex.uz/acts/916203>
2. [https://nrm.uz/contentf?doc=81212_energetika_obektlari_davlat_kadastri_ni_yuritish_tartibi_to'g'risida_nizom_\(o'zr_vm_30_06_2005_y_152-son_qaroriga_5-ilova\)](https://nrm.uz/contentf?doc=81212_energetika_obektlari_davlat_kadastri_ni_yuritish_tartibi_to'g'risida_nizom_(o'zr_vm_30_06_2005_y_152-son_qaroriga_5-ilova))
3. Хакимов А.М. Проблемы кадастрового учета земельных участков под линейными объектами // Опыт, анализ, практика. 2021. № 2.

